

SUCCESSION AND INHERITANCE RIGHT: WOMEN, PROPERTY, AND MATERIALS TRANSFER IN IGBO LAND

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Abstract: In the Igbo society, the customary law regulates the succession and inheritance rights of women. The principle of primogeniture and the cultural practice of patriarchy are held supreme at the detriment of women. This has, in recent times, raised issues concerning women, property, and the transfer of materials in Igbo land. This paper presents an in-depth literature review of the administration of succession and inheritance rights in Igbo land. It adopted a qualitative and thematic approach, explaining the meanings of succession, inheritance rights, and customary law; the Igbo people and their land; inherited property; customary law and the female folk; and the implications of national, regional, and international provisions, declarations, and conventions. Recent court rulings portray better prospects for Igbo women. It was concluded that Igbo repugnant customary law rules will yield if deliberate efforts are made to change old practices.

Keywords: Succession, inheritance, right, women, property.

Introduction

Succession is a natural phenomenon established and bequeathed to man by God, making every generation of man a temporary owner of what they possess at any point in time. It is also natural that all creatures reproduce, which explains why there are still creatures on Earth and provides a relative understanding of their habitats and adaptive mechanisms. Man, as a higher and more rational being, has, over time, developed patterns to create a harmonious succession through customs and traditions universally accepted within groups, be they family, village, clan, people/tribe, nation, or world community. Locke in Eche (2019) asserted that God planted in men a strong desire to propagate their kind and to continue themselves in their prosperity. Issues concerning succession, rights, and the inheritance of property and assets have persisted and continue to evolve across local, national, regional, and international communities.

The practice of succession is the design of the creator and maker of all things visible and should be supervised and controlled by the divine and natural law, which does not discriminate among the children (whether male or female) except for reasons of seniority. In this case, maturity is to be considered and is also cogent for the effective management of the deceased person's estate. Inheritance is part of succession since both involve transmission of possessions and giving entitlement to them over a predecessor's estate at death. Emery (2009) corroborated that in Nigeria, rights that individuals possess regarding inheritance during succession are established from the interactions among the sources of law in the country-common law, customary law and Sharia law.

Customary law holds sway in many issues concerning the local people's life and has, in recent times, been found to subjugate women's rights of inheritance in many places because it is against natural justice, equity and good conscience. The Igbo customary law is one of such customary laws that have attracted responses and reactions

over women's right of inheritance and devolution of property when predecessors died in estate. It is on this note that Eche (2019) also declared that the generation we are in is experiencing a great difference as regards the sufferings of women and the discrimination against them in the Igbo society. What is the current state of women's right of inheritance, and what does the future hold for them in this regard? Which class of women is most adversely affected? These and other themes formed the focus of this paper.

Meaning of Succession, Inheritance Right, and Customary

Succession literally means to stay or remain in the place of another. It is natural for all living creatures to at least take possession of the environment of their predecessors. Animashun and Oyeneyin, in Otu and Nabubu (2021), defined succession as the transfer of property to heirs upon the owner's death. It is concerned with the transmission of possessions and belongings as well as the privilege of the deceased person in respect of his estate to his heirs and successors. Succession deals primarily with the distribution of a deceased person's estate and his successors. The University of Mustansiriyah in Iraq (n.d) described succession as the process of change in the species' (human) structure of a community over time. Succession has also been described as a mechanism of transfer of property (Maireg, 2015). Thus, the legal implication of these definition is that the deceased person does not merely pass only the property but also passes the rights and obligation attached to the property in law to his or her successor, however the word "person" is vague, and the other one "successor" literally means one(s) who live after the deceased, whether male or female. The law governing the devolution or distribution of the deceased's property is succession law, which concerns the transmission of the deceased person's rights and obligations in respect of his estate to heirs and successors (Oni, 2014). Succession can be testate or intestate. Testate succession occurs when a person has prepared a will for the distribution of his/her property before his/her death, whereas intestate succession occurs when a person dies without a valid will.

The other concept closely tied to the former is inheritance, but for the purposes of this paper, inheritance rights are discussed. Inheritance right is a concept of two distinct words, "inheritance" and "right". The root word for inheritance is "inherited", which a verb is meaning to possess or come into possession by transmission from past generations. Inheritance is a noun meaning a possession received by the same mode (transmission) or the process of inheriting; that is, possessing or receiving property. Agbo (2024) defined inheritance as property received from the estate of a deceased person, whether by descent or as a beneficiary of a will or trust. Right literally denotes powers, privileges, titles someone has, or a just and legal claim to something. The former is a noun and can be tangible or intangible (i.e., nonphysical); the latter is an instrument or tool used to receive, acquire, hold, or perform an action. In legal parlance, Agbor (2024) also viewed it as either the liberty (protected by law) to act or to abstain from acting in a specific manner, or the power (enforced by law) to compel a specific person to do or abstain from doing a particular thing.

A legal right resides in one man or a group of men (people), assented to and assisted by the state. Inheritance right, therefore, includes the liberty to receive, acquire, hold and use part or all the estate of a person who has died as provided by the community consensus (state).

Customary is an extension of another word/concept, "custom". Customs are rules of conduct obligatory on those (people) within their scope and have been established by a long period of usage. It can also refer to traditions; thus, they include traditional activities or practices related to specific aspects of people's lives. Eche (2019) cited the Evidence Act, which defines custom as a rule that, in a particular district, has, from long usage, obtained the force of law. On the other hand, customary is an adjective meaning pertaining to customs, a way of life, a tradition, or generally accepted behaviour or practice. Every primordial society in Nigeria has, over time, developed customs and traditions that continue to evolve. These eventually became the customary law governing the respective societies' activities, practices, norms and belief systems.

The Igbo People and Land in Nigeria

The Igbo people constitute one of the largest ethnic groups in Nigeria, thus one among the major three in the country – Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo. They are the indigenous people of the south – eastern part of Nigeria. They occupy the area formerly known as the Eastern Region, created at the inception of the regional government in the mid-1950s, and had Enugu as the regional capital. Currently, the Eastern Region comprises five states: Enugu State (capital: Enugu), Imo State (capital: Owerri), Abia State (capital: Umuahia), Anambra State (capital: Awka), and Ebonyi State (capital: Abakaliki). Part of them is in the Delta and Rivers States. They can also be described as the Igbo nation, as they share a common language, though with local dialectal variations. Their language forms part of the Kwa group of West African languages (Chubb in Emeasoba, 2012). Geographically, the Igbos occupy a continuous stretch of territory roughly bounded in the North by the Igala, Idoma, and Ogoja peoples, on the East by the Ibibio people, on the South by the Ijaw people, and on the West by the Edo people.

Historically, the Igbo people, as indigenous settlers in the region, have, over time, developed customs and traditions to ensure the smooth adjudication of justice, fairness, and equity, and most of the rules governing their practices were oral, preserved and handed down from generation to generation. However, these practices and traditions vary across the region, having slight differences. Consequently, inheritance and succession practices vary across localities. One thing is cardinal among these localities: the principle governing inheritance and succession has been primogeniture, and the cultural practice has been patriarchal. In fact, the Igbo society was male-dominated. Oni (2014) emphasised that the distribution of a deceased person's estate is based on the customary doctrine of inheritance and succession of property governed by the canons of lineal descent along paternal lines.

Property to be Inherited or Transferred in Igbo Land

Property literally means belongings being held or owned by an individual with the appropriate title to it, either as a gift, purchased, allocated, or inherited, as well as any other means approved by a given society. In the context of inheritance and succession among the Igbo people, the types of property that subsist are:

Land: Land is the foundation of all human social and economic activities. In economic terms, it is a distinctive factor of production. It is a natural gift bequeathed to mankind irrespective of nativity, and it includes water, air, soil, minerals, flora and fauna that are reused in the creation of products. Most often, it is held in human custody and has become a primary source of wealth, social status, and power in Africa (Emeasoba, 2012). According to Umeh in Emeasoba (2012) land is the social security of last resort for the Igbos. In this paper, land refers to fallow soil. Omezue-Nnali (2020) cited Black's Law Dictionary, which defines land as "any ground, soil, or earth, whatever, including fields, meadows, pastures, woods, moors, waters (as in rivers), marshes, and rock." Agriculture, natural resource use, and other land-related activities are key to livelihoods for the majority of Igbos. Land also has major historical, cultural, and spiritual significance, which sometimes helps explain male dominance, and is revered as a deity.

Houses/Buildings: Most often, houses are not separated from land; however, situations abound where a person inherits the house embedded on land, and another inherits a follow-up parcel of land beside it. It must be emphasized that land is the basis for shelter on which houses are built. In the context of inheritance of a deceased person's houses, it refers to the building(s) owned or to which he/she was entitled while alive.

It includes bungalows, story buildings, huts, mud and temporary structures, one-room apartments, and single- or multi-roomed structures, but excludes those held under a tenancy or lease agreement. Buildings made for businesses which have been given out for rent are also inherited by the deceased person's successors.

Economic Plants and Trees: Economic plants and trees are parts of human possessions and belongings that are embedded on land. Igbo customary law permits separate ownership of land, on the one hand, and of the economic plants and trees growing on such land, on the other. Plants and trees here mean those that generated income to the deceased person while alive. These range from raffia palm, palm trees, orange trees, guava, plantain and

banana stands, mango trees, kolanut trees, cashew trees, pea trees, avocado trees, etc., which the deceased person(s) had ownership title while alive. At death, the plants and trees are inherited by the man or woman's successors, who then enjoy the same as the deceased person.

Farm Produce: Ukaegbu and Oguejiofor (2022) affirmed that in the Igbo society, roles like farming, hunting, building and provision of needs were delegated to the male gender, while the female was given roles related to home maintenance and child upbringing. The above assertion confirms that farming is a major occupation among the Igbos. The yields from the farm crops and livestock, including foodstuffs, constitute the farm produce. Specifically, they include cassava, vegetables, yams, cocoyams, potatoes, peppers, okro, and other crops owned by a deceased person while they were alive. The devolution and distribution of these farm products at the death of the deceased person is based on the customary law of the land or clan. Pigs or piggery, chicken or poultry, goats or tents, among other livestock, are not exempt from this process.

Money: In the context of devolution and distribution of a deceased person's belongings, money, which inter alia includes cash, debts (debtors), and bank deposits, is also property to be inherited. Debts (debtors) and bank deposits are recoverable and attainable if, before his/her death, the deceased person had regularized them with his/her debtors and banks, respectively. This money will then be distributed in accordance with the customary law of the land or clan.

Title: Title in Igbo land is a special name given to a person or group of persons in recognition of their selfless services and unprecedented activities or behaviours. It is a common practice in Igbo land, and sometimes it attracts preferential treatment in public functions. Titles can be self-assigned, such as childhood, adolescence, or youth, and are ratified by the community or clan. Titles given to a deceased person as an individual may or may not be inherited; however, titles given to a family, which take the form of family or corporate titles, are inherited, and the instrument that decides the successor to take it in the family is the customary law of the land or clan. Sometimes, the conferment or transfer of such titles is conducted by a group during public ceremonies.

The Females' Position in Igbo Customary Law of Succession and Inheritance

The female folk represent the feminine gender in society, and maleness or femaleness is an attribute of all creatures. With reference to the Holy Bible.

“So, God created man (generic) in his own image, in the image of God created he him, male and female created he them” (KJV).

Gender and gender roles have been a natural phenomenon established by God. No individual can question his/her sex image and representation because it is given and acknowledged before birth. Among the female folk, we have women and girls. In devolving or distributing the estates, possessions or belongings of a deceased person, they are called the widow, daughters, sisters or nieces.

The customary law, especially in Igbo land and culture, is held in high esteem, and its principles have been at variance with the common law and perhaps the Islamic law when issues of inheritance arise. Agbo (2024) acknowledged that until the introduction of the English law practice of writing wills, which brought about the concept of testacy, intestacy was the rule, and it was governed by customary law. The pattern of distribution of a deceased person's property is well known to the people governed by customary law. However, where a man has made an oral declaration before some persons who are witnesses, it sometimes may not prevail because the customary law is supreme in the land. The other instance is that of a dying man who made an oral declaration concerning his estate while on his sickbed. Customary laws will uphold it.

The cardinal principle of customary law of succession and inheritance among the Igbos is progeniture, which is succession by the firstborn of the same bloodline as the deceased person (Nwogugu in Oni, 2014). The rules of customary law vary across Igboland, but certain similarities remain. Upon the death of a family's founder, his eldest son, who is culturally known as ‘Okpala, Diokpala or Diokpa’, succeeds him as the head of the family

(Ngwo vs Onyejera, 1964). Some of the rules of Igbo customary law pertaining to succession and inheritance that prevail in the lands are:

1. The widow is chattel to be inherited for which the deceased person (man) has paid a sacrifice to acquire her. Thus, she does not inherit any of the man's property at his death.
2. A widow is entitled to live in the deceased husband's house as a member of the family until she remarries or dies, though she cannot alienate any part of the deceased husband's estate.
3. A widow may be permitted to manage and administer her deceased husband's estate, but she must do so with the concurrent consent of her late husband's family. The late husband's family offers her the farmland for farming, if she wishes, to feed herself.
4. The first and eldest son of the deceased person (man) succeeds him and manages or administers his estate for the benefit of himself and his brothers, or the next son; however, if that fails (where there is no son), the eldest brother of the deceased or male relative takes over (Ejiamika vs Ejiamike).
5. The widow of the deceased person (man) is inherited by the man's younger brother, and this provides a social insurance against neglect and hunger of the deceased's dependents.
6. If, for any reason, of the distribution of the estate, the deceased person's (man) sons together as a corporate body will inherit his estate.
7. Females do not have the right to inherit the estate, neither the daughter(s) nor the widow, unless the daughter on whom the *Nrachi* ceremony has been performed.
8. A daughter can only inherit where she agrees to remain unmarried in her father's house with a view to raising sons in her father's house (*Nrachi*).
9. Daughters have no right of inheritance over their mother's property. Where a wife predeceases her husband, the sons will inherit it, and failing, the husband will inherit it, and failing, the husband's male relatives.
10. While a daughter does not inherit her father's estate, she has the right to be maintained by the person who inherits her father's estate until she marries or become financially independent or dies.
11. Where a man dies without a son, brother or father, his estate will be inherited by his eldest nearest paternal male relative (Oni, 2014; Megbele, 2016; Otu & Nabiebu, 2012).

Implications of National, Regional and International Provisions, Declarations and Conventions on Rules of Igbo Customary Law of Succession and Inheritance

From the home front, Nigeria as a sovereign nation has a constitution that governs the social, economic and political affairs of her citizens. There are also regional and international declarations and conventions which Nigerian a signatory is to. Awareness has raised issues regarding succession, rights, and inheritance of materials and property at multiple levels, including among local communities, and these are beginning to challenge the rules of Igbo customary law. Cases abound in which rulings were based on the customs and practices of the people. Such cases include *Nwatia vs Ububa*, 1965, upholding patrilineal and eldest son's succession rule/custom; *Ugoma vs Ibeneme*, 1967, upholding disinheritance of females; *Nzekwu vs Nzekwu*, 1989, upholding limited rights of widows to inherit their deceased husbands' estate; *Mojekwu*, 1999, upholding disinheritance of female daughters; and *Nezianya vs Okagbue*, 1963, upholding the concurrent consent of the deceased husband's family for a widow to alienate his property or part of it.

On the contrary, the Christian Holy Bible upholds the inheritance rights of females (daughters), as Moses granted the right of inheritance to the daughters of Zelophedad. In other words, natural law upholds the right of women to inherit.

Section 42(1) of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria provided that.

“A citizen of Nigeria of a particular community, ethnic group, place or origin, sex, religion, political opinion shall not, by any reason only that he is such a person (a) be subjected either expressly by or in the practical application

of any law in force in Nigeria or any executive or administrative action of the government, to disabilities or restrictions to which citizens of Nigeria of other communities, ethnic groups, places or origin, sex, religion or political opinion are not made subject”.

To buttress the rights of women relative to those of their male counterparts, Articles 1, 5, 7, and 17 of the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights state that.

- All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.
 - No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.
 - All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law.
- (i) Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others.
- (ii) No one should be arbitrarily deprived of his property

In the same manner, the Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in its articles opposed all forms of racial discrimination against women, which from time immemorial have been rooted in Africa and Nigeria in particular. Article 5(a) states that everyone has the right to equality before the law without distinction as to race, colour and national or ethnic origin, including the right to own property alone as well as in association with others and the right to inherit. However, this is far from reality, particularly with respect to the right to inherit property and estate, as it is common in Igbo land, where the disinheritance of females is practised with impunity under the guise of customs and traditions. This is inconsistent with the provisions of the Constitution, declarations, and conventions of regional and international bodies (Silas, 2017).

Article 13(a) recognises the right to family benefits, emphasising the entitlement of all members of a family (male and female) to access such benefits, including land and housing. The property of a deceased husband is an entitlement/benefit to all members of his family, including his wife, sons and daughter, who should be the immediate beneficiaries. Furthermore, Article 16(h) guarantees the same right to both spouses with respect to ownership, acquisition, management, administration, enjoyment, and disposition of property, whether free of charge or for valuable consideration. Women’s property seems not to be acknowledged as theirs based on cultural beliefs and undue suppression if they publicly assume property ownership in their matrimonial home.

The implications of all these include that females are not citizens of the community and indeed Nigeria, and that females are less of human beings. The fact remains that females are also offspring and members of their father's or grandfather's family. Every woman is a daughter of a family and should be given the right to inheritance of her deceased father’s estate, which she will enjoy if the occasion demands. Young daughter of a deceased father who had been predeceased by his wife suffer much social and economic predicaments. This may partly explain the challenge most Igbo daughters face today to get an education and be married soon after their father dies, thus encouraging underage marriage. In recognition and recourse to rational reasoning in tandem with the natural justice, equity and good conscience, Justice Moses A. Bello gave a judgment in *Ukeje vs Ukeje*, 2018. The same is true of the Supreme Court judgement in *Anekwe vs Anekwe*, 2014.

Prospects for Igbo Women

Recent Supreme Court rulings disapproving of the discriminatory practices against Igbo women as it pertains to inheritance rights are a leeway for the female folk to agitate for their rights when they lose a deceased husband or father. Eche (2019) summed it up that many people, including women themselves, are still living in ignorance of recent developments invalidating the laws limiting women's right of inheritance in Igbo land. They are still not aware that this law (customary law) of inheritance has been abolished. Although it is encountering resistance and mixed reactions from male counterparts, civilisation is now granting women equal status in social and administrative spheres and is demanding that all allow women to inherit their husbands’ and fathers’ estates for

the progress of the family. Both males and females require a reorientation of their psyche to sustain this change. The concept of marriage to the groom's family and the bride's family must also change since the development will have a far-reaching effect and resolution on inlaw's relationship. For this to succeed:

- Women and men organisations at various levels of the Igbo land must harmonise the implications of national, regional and international provisions, declarations and conventions.
- The mass media have a role to play in presenting real-life situations when women have effectively and successfully moved the family forward after the death of their husbands with little or no oversight from their husbands' families.
- Women should stand, defend and demand their right of inheritance even if to seek redress when disinheritance occurs.
- Every girl-child, a daughter of a deceased father, should demand education, to any level, as a right and be given leverage in terms of accommodation or economic resources/sponsorship to achieve this.

Conclusion

The paper presented and reviewed issues surrounding succession and inheritance rights, particularly regarding customs and practices that affect women in Igbo land, both historically and in the present, in the context of property and material transfer. Igbo society is primogeniture and patriarchal. The customary law of the people, which upholds this principle and culture, has for time immemorial subjugated the rights of women, especially when they lost their husbands and fathers. This is against nature, the constitution of Nigeria, and regional and international declarations and conventions; thus, it has been invalidated by recent court rulings as being against natural justice, equity, and good conscience. Awareness is now growing among women of their inheritance rights. There is a bright light at the other end of the tunnel: if women are given their rightful place in our society, the prospects are bright.

Recommendations

It is the stand of this paper to recommend that more sensitization exercises through the radio, television, newspapers and electronic social media should be engaged to change the perception of Igbo people of Nigeria. The judiciary should use its position as the interpreters of the law to consolidate the precedents they have set with recent court rulings.

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